

Computational Study of 4-(2-2,6-bis (2-Carbamothionylhydrazone) Cyclohexylidene)hydrazinyl) Benzoic Acid

Ibrahim Isah NASIDI^{1*} and Memet ŞEKERCİ¹

¹ Firat University, Faculty of Science, Department of Chemistry, Elazığ, TÜRKİYE

*Corresponding author: sinonasidi@yahoo.com

Abstract

In this research a comprehensive study of 4-(2-2,6-bis (2-carbamothionylhydrazone) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid was conducted using theoretical first principle. The ligand was chosen due to its crucial importance as hormone for neurotransmitting process in the animal body. Many bases set and functional were used for the optimization of the compound to attain stability and find the suitable energy point for the overall calculations. The theoretical result was then compared with the experimental result to obtain the accuracy of the calculations. Due to the changes in the electronic properties the spectroscopic method was applied. The spectroscopic methods include determination of the bandgap energy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and infrared spectroscopy (IR) and ultraviolet spectroscopy (UV).

Keywords: Dopamine, DFT, Hatree-Fock, bandgap, Humo-Lumo and spectroscopy

Introduction

One of the main function of 4-(2-2,6-bis (2-carbamothionylhydrazone) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid in animals especially human beings is the neuro transmitting process which is the ability to send signals from brain to nerves cells and vice versa [1, 2]. Some researchers suggested that dopamine serve as a memory storage in the brain, control incoming noise to the body and regulate human character [3]. Majority of the diseases associated with the brain and nervous system is related to the malfunction of dopamine in the body. Such diseases include Parkinson disease (PD) resulted from improper or insufficient release of dopamine in the brain and Schizophrenia disease (SD) which is resulted from the change in the level of dopamine the body system of the body [4-7].

2. Computational procedure

The 4-(2-2,6-bis (2-carbamothionylhydrazone) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid figure was drawn using gauss view 9.0 and two methods were applied to optimized the structure (DFT and Hatree-Fock) using eight basis set and functionals to achieve convergence and stability of the molecule[7]. The method was implemented by different papers to describe geometries and energies of a noncovalent systems. The ground state geometry optimization of the ligand was done with DFT using hybrid functional B3LYP at various basis set; STO-3G, 3-21G, 6-31G, 6-31G*, 6-311G, LanL2MB, LanL2DZ, SDD. The frequency calculation was determined using the optimized structure to obtain the minimum on the potential energy surface [7]. Furthermore, the UV is also determined using the optimized structure. The plotting of the three dimensional mapping of the molecular orbitals is done by the B3LYP/6-311G basis set [8-9]. At the

B3LYP/6-311G basis sets, the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energies are calculated. All calculations in this paper are performed using the Gaussian 09 program [12-14]. During the stability check there is appearance of resonance in the benzene ring instead of conjugated cyclic double bond. This indicate that there is a strong bond between the atoms of the molecule after optimization.

Figure 1. Optimized molecular structure of 4-(2-(2,6-bis(2-carbamothionylhydrazono) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid

Figure 2. Frontier molecular orbital of 4-(2-(2,6-bis(2-carbamothionylhydrazono) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid

3. Result and discussion

The dopamine figure was drawn using gauss view 9.0 and two methods were applied to optimized the structure (DFT and Hatree-Fock) using eight basis set and functionals to achieve convergence and stability of the molecule. During the stability check there is appearance of resonance in the benzene ring instead of conjugated cyclic double bond. This indicate that there is a strong bond between the atoms of the molecule after optimization.

3.1 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)

The vibrational frequencies of the dopamine molecule in this work were analyse using DFT/B3LYP along with 6-311G basis set. Gauss-view molecular visualization software was initially use to plot the infrared then Origin graphing and analysis software is used to plot the fourier transform infrared spectroscopy vibrational band. The comparison between the normal dopamine and then doped with members of halogen group can be observe from figure 4.

The benzene ring present in the dopamine molecule can be investigated from the bonds of C-H, C-C and C=C ring vibrational modes. The C-H stretching vibrations of dopamine occurs about 3000 cm^{-1} and there is also a present of weak to moderate bands (multiplicity) when compared with normal C-H stretching [17-19]. In this work, the vibrational modes were calculated theoretically in the range $3065\text{-}3124\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This shows an excellent and precise agreement with experimental results.

The normal aliphatic C-H stretching was detected theoretically at about $2867\text{-}2973\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [20]. In the work, C-H stretching in ascorbic acid was calculated at $2979\text{-}3046\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for B3LYP while $1259, 1193$ and 1147 cm^{-1} bands are for C-H in-plane bending vibration in the dopamine molecule. The theoretical results obtained from the B3LYP model are close to the true value which is the indication of the accuracy of the model.

The C-C stretching vibration in the ring has different values due to the nature of the ring but in most cases it ranges from $1600, 350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [18]. The value has little increase due to the DFT methods approximation in this work and was found to at $1680, 1444$ and 1365 cm^{-1} .

3.2 Proton magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H-NMR}$)

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is a spectroscopic technique use to determine the chemical enviroment of the protons present in the molecule under considerations. The two auto protons have peak at around $7.88\text{-}8.01\text{ppm}$ due to the closeness with carboxylic acid carbon while the two meta protons absorbed at around 7.05ppm as result of distance with the carboxylic carbon. The single proton attached to the bridged nitrogen atom has a peak at around 10.98ppm due to the electronegative properties of the nitrogen. $8.09\text{-}8.65\text{ppm}$ peak belongs to the two protons attached to the nitrogen atom (NH2) attached to hexane group. The peak at $14.86\text{-}13.12\text{ppm}$ is attributed to the single attached to the nitrogen atom of the hexane molecule.

Figure 3. Comparison of FT-IR absorbance spectra of 4-(2-(2,6-bis (2-carbamothionylhydrazone) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid between theoretical and experimental results.

Figure 4. Comparison of ¹H-NMR of 4-(2-2,6-bis (2-carbamothionylhydrazone) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid between theoretical and experimental results

3.2 Carbon nuclear magnetic resonance (¹³C-NMR)

Just like proton NMR, carbon nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is a spectroscopic technique used to determine the chemical environment of the carbon atoms present in the molecule under consideration. The peak at 166.88 ppm is attributed to the carboxylic acid carbon atom. The peak at 131.12 ppm is the peak of the two auto carbon atoms on the benzene ring while the peak at 115.09 ppm is attributed to meta carbon atoms on the benzene ring and 124 ppm belongs to para carbon atoms. 148.74-146.63 ppm is the peak that is the result of absorption of auto carbon in the hexane ring while 26.71-33.48 ppm belong to meta carbon and 19.18 ppm belongs to para carbon in the hexane molecule. Due to the electronegative nature of nitrogen and sulphur atoms, 182.02-178.63 ppm belong to carbon that is bonded to two nitrogens and double bonded to sulphur atoms.

Figure 5. Comparison of ^{13}C -NMR of 4-(2-(2,6-bis(2-carbamothionylhydrazono) cyclohexylidene) hydrazinyl) benzoic acid between theoretical and experimental results

4. Conclusion

This research analyse the basic properties of dopamine (including bandgap, density of states and spectroscopic properties) and it is then doped with the first three members of halogen group to compare the change in electronic and other spectroscopic parameters. Different basis set in DFT and Hatree-Fock were used in the optimization process to determine the lowest energy and suitable basis set for the whole calculation of the ascorbic acid, then later the compound was doped with the first three halogens members separately. Spectroscopic properties were determined such as uv-vis and NMR for both the doped and the undoped dopamine. Finally, the FTIR spectra of the dopamine with different doping with halogens group was investigated by theoretical method. It was found that the bandgap is sensitive to the doping as we moved down the group members (the bandgap depends on the electronegativity of the halogens members).

References

- [1] Goldman-Rakic, P.S., E.C. Muly III, and G.V. Williams, D₁ receptors in prefrontal cells and circuits. *Brain Research Reviews*, 2000.
- [2] Nicola, S.M., D.J. Surmeier, and R.C. Malenka, Dopaminergic modulation of neuronal excitability in the striatum and nucleus accumbens. *Annual review of neuroscience*, 2000. 23(1): p. 185-215.
- [3] Santos-García, D., M. Prieto-Formoso, and R. de la Fuente-Fernández, Levodopa dosage determines adherence to long-acting dopamine agonists in Parkinson's disease. *Journal of the neurological sciences*, 2012. 318(1-2): p. 90-93.
- [4] Barforushi, M.M., S. Safari, and M. Monajjemi, Nano Biotechnology Study of X-Dopamine Complexes (X= Co²⁺, Au³⁺, Pt²⁺, and Pd²⁺). *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience*, 2015. 12(10): p. 3058-3065.
- [5] Aliste, M.P., Theoretical study of dopamine. Application of the HSAB principle to the study of drug–receptor interactions. *Journal of Molecular Structure: THEOCHEM*, 2000. 507(1-3): p. 1-10.
- [6] Fellous, J.-M. and R. Suri, Dopamine, roles of. *The handbook of brain theory and neural networks*, 2003: p. 361-365.
- [7] Mehdizadeh Barforushi, M. and K. Zare, A Theoretical Study on Dopamine: Geometry, energies and NMR. *Journal of Physical & Theoretical Chemistry*, 2014. 11(2): p. 57-61.
- [8] Gingrich, J.A. and M.G. Caron, Recent advances in the molecular biology of dopamine receptors. *Annual review of neuroscience*, 1993. 16(1): p. 299-321.
- [9] Barforushi, M.M., NMR and NBO investigation of Dopamine properties in point view of Brain activities. *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 2014. 30(4): p. 1823- 1840.
- [10] Raghu, P., et al., A novel horseradish peroxidase biosensor towards the detection of dopamine: A voltammetric study. *Enzyme and microbial technology*, 2014. 57: p. 8-15.
- [11] Sun, W., et al., Poly (methylene blue) functionalized graphene modified carbon ionic liquid electrode for the electrochemical detection of dopamine. *Analytica chimica acta*, 2012. 751: p. 59-65.
- [12] Yu, D., et al., A novel electrochemical sensor for determination of dopamine based on AuNPs@ SiO₂ core-shell imprinted composite. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2012. 38(1): p. 270-277.
- [13] Zhai, C., et al., Experimental and theoretical study on the interaction of dopamine hydrochloride with H₂O. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 2016. 215: p. 481-485.
- [14] Chen, S., K.Y. Tai, and R.D. Webster, The Effect of the Buffering Capacity of the Supporting Electrolyte on the Electrochemical Oxidation of Dopamine and 4 - Methylcatechol in Aqueous and Nonaqueous Solvents. *Chemistry–An Asian Journal*, 2011. 6(6): p. 1492-1499.
- [15] Mamand, D., Determination the band gap energy of poly benzimidazobenzophenanthroline and comparison between HF and DFT for three different basis sets. *Journal of Physical Chemistry and Functional Materials*. 2(1): p. 31-35.
- [16] Frisch, M.J., J.A. Pople, and J.S. Binkley, Self consistent molecular orbital methods 25. Supplementary functions for Gaussian basis sets. *The Journal of chemical physics*, 1984. 80(7): p. 3265-3269.